

Personal Variables and Senior Secondary School Students' Hygiene Practices in Calabar Education Zone, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined the influence of personal variables on hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in Calabar Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. The study adopted the inferential survey research design. The study was guided by three null hypotheses. The population consisted of 20,470 (9,331 males and 11,139 females) senior secondary school students of 81 public secondary schools during the 2016/2017 academic session. The study adopted the stratified random sampling technique in selecting a sample of 819 students. Data analysis was done using descriptive statistics. Personal Variables on Hygiene Practices Questionnaire (PVHPQ) was the instrument used for data collection. The data collected were analysed using an independent t-test and ANOVA analysis tested at .05 levels of significance. The study revealed that there is a significant influence of gender, age and self-concept on secondary school students' hygiene practices in the area of study. The study concluded that female students are more conscious of hygiene practices than their male counterparts. Children of school age were generally less conscious about hygiene practices. The study also concluded that good hygiene practices help to reduce the risk of ill-health and equally boost levels of confidence and self-esteem. The study recommended that Parents should always do the needful in educating their children on the benefits of proper personal hygiene as well as finding out what their children are doing at a particular time, if they have washed their clothes, barb their hairs among others, irrespective of their age.

Keywords: Hygiene, personal variables, practices, secondary school, self-concept, student hygiene.

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Introduction

Without good health, life cannot function at full capacity. Health, as explained by World Health Organization (WHO) (2010) is the state of complete physical, mental and social well-being of an individual and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Good hygienic standards promote health and that is why personal hygiene is a prerequisite for human wellbeing. Personal hygiene is assessed by examining the attitude of individuals towards hand washing, regular

bathing, cutting of nails, washing of clothes as well as attitude towards care for the teeth, among others. Many people including adults and school children are negligent to the neglect of basic personal hygiene. Which can manifest in such symptoms as general illness; bad breath, body odour. This could lead to depression, low self-confidence, as well as having a negative consequence for the child long term overall development.

A substantial proportion of the total infectious disease burden worldwide is due to direct hand to mouth transmission of germs, via food, handshaking with infected person or transmission through particles resulting from sneezing vomiting and other fluid. These infections are preventable by proper personal hygiene practices, which play a part in reducing the spread as well as serves as a defensive strategy against the future epidemic. Proper personal hygiene is therefore important as a first-line defence, as well as a primary weapon to mitigate the spread of pathogens in human and the environment. Regrettably, adherence to proper personal hygiene practices such as regular washing of hands, cutting of fingernails washing and sunning of cloths after use, brushing of teeth among others as often as it should be, is unacceptably low among adolescence (Curtis, 2016).

Students have in several ways which may be as a result of negligent or ignorance engage in poor personal hygiene practices ranging from the poor or negative attitude toward bathing, washing of hands, brushing of teeth, washing and sunning of cloths after use, cutting of nails, etc. This can lead to harbouring of intestinal worms which could expose one to infections, transient flora, scabies, ringworm, hepatitis B, Diarrhoea among others. (Slade, 2013). William (2017) noted that, in the course of students going about their daily activities, there are being confronted with germs through what they get hold of, the kind of food they eat, the people they come in contact with, the water they drink, what they wear, oil secretion from the skin, and the environment they found ourselves, among others. He explained that if these are not properly handled will form a suitable atmosphere and convenient home for germs to survive, grow, multiply and get into the body which put their health at risk.

This is evidenced by Infection Control Guidelines that observed that washing of hands with soap regularly prevents acute and lower respiratory tract infection which is the leading causes of disease and death globally. Therefore, failures to adhere to appropriate hygiene practices make disease transmission very easy. More so, institutional settings such as child care centre, hospital and schools are an ideal environment for the transmission of infectious disease because they bring susceptible individuals into close contact with others. Therefore, promoting good hygiene practices among students is the most important measure to improve public health. This will also assist in helping the school children to assume responsibility for their health, as well as reduce human suffering and financial losses from infectious disease.

However, Government and non-governmental organizations have tried to ensure that hygienic practices are enhanced and maintained through a multitude of programs and campaigns which are ongoing, for the eradication and control of infectious diseases. For instance, health education is entrenched in the curriculum of students, the global handwashing day has been calling for improved hygiene practices both locally and globally with the guiding

vision being a culture of regular washing of hands with soap. While health talks are often organized in town halls and even in churches; radio jingles and billboards are also mounted on the street to sensitize the youths and other individuals on how to maintain healthy hygienic practices (Slade, 2014). Despite these efforts, the problem still exists. What has continually occupied the minds of researchers, parents and government is why these various efforts to equip the young people with knowledge and practice of personal hygiene have not yielded desired result commensurate to these efforts.

Poor personal hygiene has been observed to have a great influence on the self-concept and overall health of people. Ormrod (2016) posited that self-concept is one's belief in his or her ability to succeed in a specific situation despite barriers, particularly in hygiene practices. He further stressed that self-concept affects every area of human endeavour. It determines the belief a person holds regarding his power to affect situations, the power a person has to face challenges, competency, and the choices a person is most likely to make. Tones (2014) stated that, male and female students have unique hygiene needs, that if ignored may lead to health problems. Women must take care of their genitals to keep them clean. They must be taught to always clean their genitals after using the restroom, to prevent introducing infections from the rectum to the urethra. The scholar also noted that only 15 to 18% of the population is least prepared for its onset, and are ignorant of the hygienic management of the processes and their importance. This poverty of awareness and preparedness may endanger their reproductive health.

The author further stressed that the less fortunate proportion of women with poor hygiene knowledge and insufficient resources are vulnerable to diseases when they collect their period with a used piece of cloth of unknown sanitary quality. Mostly in rural areas, adolescents and even older women use a piece of cotton cloth as a pad during menstruation. After use, it is washed and kept in some dark corner of the house so that no one will see it, and sunlight which is necessary to kill some germs is denied. What has continually occupied the minds of some researchers, parents and government is what probably could be the causes of this problem. The researcher, thus, presumes that this situation can be traced to personal variables of individuals. There this study delved to ascertain whether personal variables influence student's hygiene practices in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.

Empirically, Rosen and Brown (2012) found that the hygiene level of a person is dependents on sex and biological nature. For example, during menstruation, which is not present in men, the women practice a very high level of proper hygiene, in changing their pad at least three times a day, taking regular bath and hand washing. Willer (2015) found that hand sanitiser use was low among boys than girls and 30% of female used paper towel as the most common hand drying material, and 10.1% of boys were found using their pocket as a hand drying material. The researcher submitted that female student is more conscious of hand washing and drying than their male counterpart. This is similar to the findings of Donsberger (2013) who revealed that females are more informed and practice good oral hygiene behaviour to a higher degree than male. However, Bateman (2014) argued that gender has no bearing on general hygiene practices. Bateman's study reported that 97.2% of both male and female brush

their teeth twice a day; wash their hands regularly, especially after defecation as well as taking their bath as required because the hygiene material was available. The result of Bateman was maintained by William (2017) who reported that gender has no significant influence on individual hygiene practices.

In terms of age, Birks (2015) found that age is nothing but a number and it has no significant influence on students' hygiene practices, rather a knowledge, location, financial status and attitude plays a vital role in hygiene practices. According to the findings of Slade (2014), while location, gender was significantly associated with hygiene practices, no significant influence of age on hygiene practices was revealed. A report from WHO (2014) indicated that thought, has not been fully adhered to, especially by adolescence of school age, children of school age generally less conscious about hygiene practices. In contrast, Davies (2014) revealed that gender, age and self-esteem significantly influence personal hygiene practices. The study also revealed a significant difference between children of 6-10 years and 10-15 years with regards to their hygiene practices.

Machango (2001) perceived self-concept as a set of perceptions or reference points that the student has about himself, a set of characteristics, attributes, qualities and deficiencies, capacities and limits, values and relationships that the student knows to be descriptive of himself and which he perceives as data concerning his identity. Tabbner (2016) noted that individuals who already have low self-esteem and depression often neglect personal hygiene practices, which perpetuates the problem of poor body image. As observed by Asma, Manzoor and Muhammad (2010) hygiene is a common practice that makes individual feel different from each other. The study of Goodman (2012) revealed that physical, social, educational orientation, religion and self-concept are statistically significant on students' hygiene practices. Implications of Goodman (2012) indicated that all components of self-concept had a significant influence on the students' hygiene practices. A study on academics revealed that students with high academic self-concept significantly had a more positive attitude towards schooling than students with low academic self-concept. (Akubuiro, 2012). It can be inferred from Akubuiro (2012) that students with high self-concept may possess favourable hygiene practices.

From the ongoing, an argument persists in the literature. Studies have reported the relationship between personal variables. For example, some studies argued that gender and age do significantly influence students' hygiene practices. some studies revealed that gender significantly influences hygiene practices with most studies favouring female (Donsberger, 2013). Therefore, this study is set to assess the influence of personal variables on hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in Calabar Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. The findings of this study may be of great benefit to the students, general public, school management, curriculum planners and the society at large. To students, the finding may enable them identify the problems associated with poor hygiene practices, which could help them to identify the extent to which adherence to proper hygiene practices could provide optimum health by preventing infectious disease. To the general public the study will provide information for proper sanitation practices and the need for proper hygiene practices among households. Government, through the school management will through the findings and

recommendation of this study, create infection free environment for students and provide an avenue for public health campaign on hygiene practices among students. Curriculum planners will through the findings see to the need to include hygiene practices in school curricula to be taught to students. This would build the necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes on hygiene practices among students. Specifically, this study is defined by the following objectives:

- i. gender influence hygiene practices among senior secondary school students.
- ii. age of senior secondary school students influences their hygiene practices.
- iii. self-concept of students influences their hygiene practices.

Statement of hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested statistically.

- i. Gender has no significant influence on hygiene practices among secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.
- ii. There is no significant influence of age on hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone.
- iii. Self-concept does not significantly influence hygiene practices among secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State.

Methods

Research design

An inferential survey research design was adopted for this study. The design was considered appropriate for the study since the sample was obtained from the population and the result obtained was generalized to the entire population. The data for the study was collected through a structured questionnaire designed specifically for this study.

Population and sample

The population consisted of all senior secondary school students of 81 public secondary schools from the seven Local Government Areas in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River state. With a total number of about 20,470 (9,331 males and 11,139 females) students during the 2016/2017 academic session. The study adopted the stratified random sampling technique. In doing so, the schools in the area were first grouped into seven strata based on the Local Government Area. The researcher randomly selected 20% of the schools in each of the LGAs through the hat and draw method (balloting) and the schools selected constituted the sampled schools. This summed up to the selection of 819 students for the investigation. However, the sample size of 819 students was regarded as large enough for the generalization of the result gotten for the findings of the data analyses.

Instrumentation

The instrument that was used for data collection is a researcher-made questionnaire titled: personal variables and hygiene practices questionnaire (PVHPQ). The instrument was divided into two sections: A and B. Section A of the instrument consist of the Bio-data of the respondents, which elicited information on the parental economic level, gender and age while section B consisting of 19 items, designed to measure self-concept and hygiene practices on a four-point Likert scale. The instrument was validated by four experts' two each from Measurement and Evaluation and Human Kinetics and Health Education Department, for face and content validity. Their observations on ambiguous items in the questionnaire that contained 15 items were trimmed to 12 after scrutiny and the instrument was ascertained to be valid. A reliability estimate was conducted to determine the consistency of the instrument. The instrument was trial tested on 50 students, outside the ones sampled for the study. Cronbach alpha estimate method was employed in analysing the data. The coefficient of the reliability estimate obtained ranged from .72 to .80

Procedure for data collection and analyses

The instruments were administered to the sampled students. The researcher explained in detail what the questionnaire sought to achieve and allowed the children to decide whether to participate in the study or not. In the end, 763 copies out of the initial 819 copies of the questionnaires administered to the students were successfully collected. This amounted to a 93.16% return rate. The data collected were analysed using Independent t-test analysis and One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) tested at .05 levels of significance.

Results

Hypothesis one

Gender has no significant influence on hygiene practices among secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. The hypothesis was analysed using an Independent t-test analysis tested at a .05 level of significance. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 1. The result in Table 1 revealed that the mean score obtained for the 368 male subjects as regards hygiene practices was 31.24 with a standard deviation of 5.76 is less than the mean score of 32.63 with a standard deviation of 4.97 obtained for the 395 female subjects. The mean difference was statistically significant since the obtained t-value of 3.572 in the absolute sense with a p-value of .000 met the criterion for significance at .05 level. This shows that male students in public schools in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State differ significantly from their female counterparts as regards hygiene practices in favour of the females.

Table 1: Independent t-test analysis of gender and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Sex	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-level
Male	368	31.24	5.76	-3.572*	.000
Female	395	32.63	4.97		

*Significant at .05 level; $p < .05$.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant influence of age on hygiene practices among senior secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone. Based on this, the influence of age on hygiene practices was computed using One-way ANOVA as shown in Table 2. The result presented in Table 2 revealed the mean score obtained by the subjects who are below the age of 15 years as regards to their hygiene practices was 33.36 with a standard deviation of 5.67 which is greater than the mean score of 32.46 with a standard deviation of 4.44 obtained by the subjects who are between the ages of 15 – 17 and this is greater than the mean score of 29.18 with a standard deviation of 6.29 obtained by the subjects who are above 17 years of age was. This implies that the higher the age of the subjects, the lesser their hygiene practices. The result further revealed that the calculated F-value of 32.440 obtained with a p-value of .000 was seen to be greater than F-value tabulated (3.00) with the degrees of freedom of 2 and 760 at a .05 significance level. Therefore, this study rejected the null hypothesis based on the F-values and concluded that age in hygiene practices is significant. Given the significant F-value, the Fishers least significance difference (LSD) was employed as a post hoc test as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. One-way Analysis of Variance of age and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Age	N	Mean	SD		
Below 15 Years	185	33.36	5.67		
15 – 17 Years	411	32.46	4.44		
Above 17 Years	167	29.18	6.29		
Total	763	31.96	5.41		
Source Of Variance	SS	Df	MS	F-Ratio	P-Level
Between Groups	1754.588	2	877.294	32.440*	.000
Within Groups	20553.15	760	27.044		
Total	22307.74	762			

*Significant at .05 alpha level; $p < .05$.

The result in Table 3 revealed that there was no significant mean difference in hygiene practices between subjects who are below 15 years and those who are between the ages of 15 – 17 years ($MD = .90$, $p > .05$). A significant mean difference exists in hygiene practices between subjects who are below 15 years and those who are above 17 years of age ($MD = 4.18$, $p < .05$). Also, a significant mean difference exists in hygiene practices between subjects who are between the ages of 15 – 17 years and those who are above 17 years of age ($MD = 3.28$, $p < .05$).

Table 3. Fishers Least Significance Difference (LSD) for age and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Age	N	Mean	MD	p-level
Below 15 years	185	33.36	.90	.052
15 – 17 years	411	32.46		
Below 15 years	185	33.36	4.18*	.000
Above 17 years	167	29.18		
15 – 17 years	411	32.46	3.28*	.000
Above 17 years	167	29.18		

*Significant at .05 level; $p < .05$.

Hypothesis Three

Self-concept does not significantly influence hygiene practices among secondary school students in the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. Based on this, the influence of self-concept on hygiene practices was computed using One-way ANOVA as shown in Table 4. The result presented in Table 4 revealed the mean score obtained by the subjects who have low self-concept as regards to their hygiene practices was 29.40 with a standard deviation of 6.95 which is less than the mean score of 32.23 with a standard deviation of 4.96 obtained by the subjects who have a moderate level of self-concept and this is less than the mean score of 33.21 with a standard deviation of 4.27 obtained by the subjects who have a high level of self-concept. This implies that the higher the self-concept of the students, the higher their hygiene practices. The result further revealed that the calculated F-value of 26.460 obtained with a p-value of .000 was seen to be greater than F-value tabulated (3.00) with the degrees of freedom of 2 and 760 at a .05 significance level. Therefore, this study rejected the null hypothesis based on the F-values and concluded that self-concept on hygiene practices is significant. Given the significant F-value, the Fishers least significance difference (LSD) was employed as a post hoc test as shown in Table 5.

Table 4. One-way Analysis of Variance of self-concept and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Self-concept	N	Mean	SD		
Low	159	29.4	6.95		
Moderate	358	32.23	4.96		
High	246	33.21	4.27		
Total	763	31.96	5.41		
Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-ratio	p-level
Between groups	1452.203	2	726.101	26.460*	.000
Within groups	20855.54	760	27.441		
Total	22307.74	762			

*Significant at .05 alpha level; $p < .05$.

The result in Table 5 revealed that there was a significant mean difference in an absolute sense in hygiene practices between subjects whose self-concept is low and those whose self-concept is moderate (MD = -2.83, $p < .05$). A Significant mean difference in hygiene practices also exists in absolute sense between subjects whose self-concept is low and those whose self-concept is high (MD = -3.81, $p < .05$). Also, a significant mean difference in an absolute sense

exists in hygiene practices between subjects whose self-concept is moderate and those whose self-concept is high (MD = -.98, $p < .05$).

Table 5. Fishers Least Significance Difference (LSD) for self-concept and hygiene practices among secondary school students in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State

Self-concept	N	Mean	MD	p-level
Low	159	29.40	-2.83*	.000
Moderate	358	32.23		
Low	159	29.40	-3.81*	.000
High	246	33.21		
Moderate	358	32.23	-.98*	.025
High	246	33.21		

*Significant at .05 level; $p < .05$.

Discussion

This research hypothesis which addresses the influence of gender on students' hygiene practices revealed that there is a significant influence of gender on secondary school students' hygiene practices in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. This might be as a result of the fact that female students allocate more time in taking care of their body, always conscious of what they wear, and how they look because it is in their nature to look neat and clean to attract attention or to be noticed by others which they appreciate so much unlike the male. This result conforms with Willer (2015) that female students are more conscious in hand washing, brushing their teeth, hair among others than their male counterparts. Female students in comparison to male folks significantly use medium strength toothbrush, brushed their teeth more than once daily and choose toothpaste following dentist recommendations. Female participants significantly gave good attention to their oral hygiene practices than the male ones.

This result also supports Slade (2014) who observed that oral disease constitutes public health problem among men than women in developing countries due to lack of attention given to oral hygiene practices by men, stressing that they wake up in the morning, what they think of is how to meet up the challenges of the day and returning home late and tired that would not allow them to do this needful as regard to brushing of teeth twice a day. This result is also in tandem with the finding of Rosen and Brown (2012) that proper hygiene does not end at public appearance or outwards look. An individual's inner wears, clothes, surroundings, how/what he eats, drinks etc have a lot to say on hygiene, which is a lifestyle and not a show, stressing that the hygiene level of a person is dependents on the sex and biological nature.

For example, during menstruation, which is not present in men, the women practice a very high level of proper hygiene, changing their pad at least three times a day, taking a regular bath and hand washing. Most Women do not repeat their underwears they make sure they are dry cleaned after use, because of the normal or abnormal discharge that sometimes occurs in them, but all these are not practised by the male. This result negates the finding of Bateman (2014) who noted that gender has no control on general hygiene practices, stressing that if both

groups of students are placed in the same condition as well as given the same opportunity with equal hygiene practices facilities, they will certainly practice good hygiene.

The research hypothesis which addresses the influence of age on students' hygiene practices revealed that there is a significant influence of age on secondary school students' hygiene practices in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. This implies that age has a significant influence on hygiene practices and that the higher the age of the subjects, the lesser their hygiene practices. Naturally, one may have thought that the higher the age of an individual the higher their hygiene practices believing that one does not expect an individual of 20 years above to eat fruit without washing, visiting the toilet without washing their hands, or not washing their uniform regularly the same way a child of 10 years should behave. This might be as a result of the fact that the younger children are still under the full control of their parents or guardian, they go as far as helping them in cutting their nails, wash their uniforms among other, they try to know if they have taken their bath, brush their teeth, wash their uniforms, because of the fear that they may be beaten if they do otherwise, they will comply. This help in fostering more hygiene practices, but as they grow older less attention will give to them by their parents believing that they know what to do so they are not been checkmated.

This result is not in agreement with the finding of WHO (2014) that hygiene practises is a milestone of infectious disease control that it has long been recognized to be the convenient, effective and also cost-effective means of preventing communicable disease but has not been given attention especially to teenage school children which may invariably post a threat to their health, stressing that hygiene practices have achieved the reputation of being a convenient means of preventing communicable disease, yet it has not been fully adhered to, especially by adolescence of school age. Children of school age were generally less conscious about hygiene practices. This result negates the finding of Birks (2015) who found that age is nothing but a number and it has no significant influence on students' hygiene practices, rather a knowledge, location, financial status and attitude plays a vital role in hygiene practices, stressing that when they are a favourable environment for proper hygiene practices age has no sole effect on hygiene practices.

The research hypothesis which addresses the influence of self-concept on students' hygiene practices revealed that there is a significant influence of self-concept on secondary school students' hygiene practices in Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State. This implies that self-concept has a significant influence on hygiene practices among students. This could largely be since the way an individual conceives himself determines what he does with his life. students who place a premium on his/herself cannot pick from the ground, cannot keep his/her clothes dirty, cannot allow their teeth to stay a day without getting them brushed as well as keep their armpit dirty. They would always ensure that they maintain healthy sanitary conditions that would promote their ego and self-identity.

This result is in tandem with Tabbner (2016) who noted that individuals who already have low self-esteem and depression often neglect personal hygiene practices, which perpetuates the problem of poor body image, stressing that good hygiene practices help to

reduce the risk of ill-health and equally boost levels of confidence and self-esteem. The chances of succeeding either in work or social settings or even with the opposite sex can be altered by poor hygiene practices. Keeping our body clean and well-presented projects a positive body image that reflects our personalities. This finding also supports Asma, Manzoor and Muhammad (2010) who observed that hygiene is a common practice that makes individual feel different from each other. A person who takes his bath regularly and dresses neat feels he/she is clean which connotes hygiene and his/her feelings determine his/her self-concept. Hygiene enhances self-concept and self-concept enhances the academic performance of students.

The result also agrees with Machango (2001) who perceived self-concept as a set of perceptions or reference points that the student has about himself, a set of characteristics, attributes, qualities and deficiencies, capacities and limits, values and relationships that the student knows to be descriptive of himself and which he perceives as features concerning his identity. Positive hygiene practices are a booster to healthy living among students while good healthy living influences high academic achievement. A healthy self-concept is a child's armour against the challenges of the world. Children who feel well about themselves do have an easier time handling conflicts and resisting negative pressures. They tend to smile more readily and enjoy life. Such children are realistic and generally optimistic. Any child who appears to be dirty and unkempt tend to have a poor relationship with peers which will affect his/her self-concept negatively. Good hygiene gives good health and good health possesses a positive self-image.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study concludes that gender and age significantly influence the hygiene practices of Secondary School Students. Female students are more conscious about hygiene practices than their male counterparts. Children of school age were generally less conscious about hygiene practices. furthermore, good hygiene practices help to reduce the risk of ill-health and equally boost levels of confidence and self-esteem. Based on these findings, the following recommendations were made.

- i. Parents and teachers should encourage the male students on the importance of cleanliness given their delicate body parts. And dedicate time to their hygiene. Government agencies should do a routine awareness campaign in schools to enhance hygiene practices among the students.
- ii. Parents should always do the needful in educating their children on the benefits of proper personal hygiene as well as finding out what their children are doing at a particular time, if they have washed their clothes, barb their hairs among others, irrespective of their age.
- iii. Parents, guardian and teachers should educate students to develop a high level of self-concept to foster their hygiene practices.

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